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Socio-Ethical Challenges of In-Vitro Fertilisation in Nigeria

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Abstract

Infertility is a socio-cultural dilemma in Nigeria. It remains a major problem affecting married couples experiencing difficulty in childbearing. It brings significant negative societal consequences on people. When a marriage does not produce children, there is a concern, and it is a horrible experience for such couples. Hence, there is a lot of anxiety for couples experiencing infertility after the first year of marriage. In-vitro fertilisation has been discovered to be one of the ways to addressing infertility challenges. This study examines the socio-ethical challenges encompassing in-vitro fertilisation in Nigeria context by examining some ethical dilemmas. The study adopted descriptive research approach. Findings revealed that third party gametes is a contention, destruction of embryo is morally wrong, sustainability of frozen embryos is reduced with longer storage time, that in-vitro fertilisation is not readily accessible to low income earners and human embryo should be treated with dignity. The study concluded that in-vitro fertilisation gives hope to couples faced with infertility challenges, that the process of IVF is not without some socio-ethical dilemmas, and that IVF as one of the means of childbearing is often contested in Nigeria cultural setting. This work recommended that there is the need for reproductive education so as to reduce stigmatisation, encouragement of seminars and conferences involving religious leaders, ethicists and medical personnel in order for in-vitro fertilisation to be acceptable in Nigeria society.

Keywords: Bioethics, Culture, Infertility, In-vitro Fertilisation

Introduction

Infertility brings significant negative societal consequences on people. A high premium is placed on childbearing in Nigeria to the extent that couples married for just a few months are expected to show the fruit of such marriage (pregnancy) within the shortest possible period. The purpose of most African marriage, especially in Nigeria, is to bear children. Hence, there is a lot of anxiety for couples experiencing infertility after the first year of marriage. Adoption is not a welcome idea as a way of childbearing in Nigeria culture. This has made couples take the option for in-vitro fertilisation (IVF). In-vitro fertilisation is an assisted reproductive technology done by taking an ovum from a woman's body, fertilising it in laboratory conditions (in-vitro), and implanting the fertilised ovum or embryo in the uterus of the woman a few days after fertilisation (Krickovic and Zotovic, 2018). In-vitro fertilisation as a method of childbearing is generating controversies, especially among religious bodies, as to whether it is right to employ such a procedure as a solution to the challenge of infertility due to some ethical issues associated with the method (Hampshire and Bob, 2015).

In Nigeria today, the patriarchal influence is the order of the day, and this is glaring in the way the problem of infertility challenges are handled, making the burden of childbearing to be solely on the woman. One of the challenges of in-vitro fertilisation is the process of exposing couples to various treatments that come along with human experimentation. Couples involved in in-vitro fertilisation treatment are exposed to stigma, and their children are not exempted. One major problem of in vitro fertilisation is that the clients are always subject to stigmatization, and this has made many in-vitro fertility clients live in secrecy, live a life of withdrawal from other people, and at the same time develop low self-esteem in society. Cousineau and Domar (2007) argued that couples facing the challenge of infertility are facing all sorts of psychological and emotional trauma. They further corroborate that women especially tend to carry the psychological burden than men as men appear to negotiate the change to a childless lifestyle more easily than their wives. Nigeria culture also stigmatizes the inability of a woman to carry a pregnancy of their own.

Despite the secularized nature of Nigeria society, religion still plays a vital role in the regulations and practices of in-vitro fertilisation. Religious bias has also become a strong challenge to in-vitro fertility as an option. However, in-vitro fertilisation has become the method of choice for conception in our contemporary times. In most cases, the woman feels and bears the shame and consequences for not bearing children. Nigeria society places a premium on

childbearing, and the same society did not see in-vitro fertilization as an option to address the challenge of infertility. This is a serious dilemma. The major problem the work intends to address is that the consequence of the inability to give birth among couples is on the increase, and most couples are prone to psychological stress resulting in anxiety, insecurity in marriage, fear, depression, seclusion/isolation, shame/disgrace, disorientation, physical pain, disheartening, and the mental well-being of couples in such conditions is adversely affected. Clients involved in in-vitro fertilisation do so in secrecy to avoid stigmatisation and to preserve their self-esteem.

Hence, the paper is set out to examine the process of in-vitro fertilisation, discover the ethical issues in in-vitro fertilisation, and find out the socio-ethical implications of in-vitro fertilisation, which eventually, rise some questions like what is the process of in-vitro fertilisation? What are the ethical issues in in-vitro fertilisation? And what are the socio-ethical implications of in-vitro fertilisation? This work will proffer conclusion and some recommendations. The work adopted the descriptive survey method. Descriptive research describes situations and events through which information that illuminates relationships, patterns and links between variables is gathered (Ogundare, 2013; Ayantayo, 2015). Descriptive method enables the researcher to gather information and involves collecting data that will accurately and objectively describe the present situation.

Theoretical Framework: Moral Theory

The theoretical framework for this article is Moral Theory. Morality is a set of principles that govern our actions concerning each other and are taken to be of a special kind. That is to say, morality controls man's conduct through rules and regulations. Morals are grounded on values that check and balance human conduct. Moral theory gives an account of right actions. It aims to provide criteria for judging actions that are grounded in or explained by values. Moral theory evaluates the permissibility of actions concerning agreement with moral principles and existing values. Hence, the procedures involved in in vitro fertilisation are key to moral theory. The ethical value of the sanctity of life and a person's dignity is paramount in moral theory.

Lee (2010), a proponent of contemporary deontological ethicists, often critiques in vitro fertilisation on moral grounds. He argues that the destruction of embryos in in-vitro fertilisation violates the ethical principle that all human life deserves protection from conception. His contributions are relevant in ongoing debates about bioethics and the status of embryos. From the viewpoint of deontological ethicists, in vitro fertilisation may raise concerns, especially

regarding the handling of embryos, which some argue should be treated with the same moral respect as persons. Following Immanuel Kant's work, Deontological ethicists judge actions based on their adherence to duty and respect for persons as ends in themselves.

In contrast, Singer (2011), a utilitarian moralist, evaluates in vitro fertilisation based on its outcomes. He sees in vitro fertilisation as ethically permissible if it maximises happiness and minimises harm. With regards to couples having the challenges of infertility, in-vitro fertilisation can bring immense joy by allowing them to have children, thus producing a positive outcome. Utilitarian ethicists stress the importance of responsible practices, including considering embryo rights and the implications of genetic selection.

Hursthoue (1999), a virtue ethicist, averred that the virtues of care and responsibility should guide decision-making in in-vitro fertilisation. She emphasised the importance of considering the broader social and emotional contexts in which such decisions are made. Virtue ethicists focus on the character of the individuals involved in decision-making rather than just the actions themselves. It involves virtues such as care, responsibility, and love. The process may be morally acceptable for a couple seeking in vitro fertilisation to nurture and love a child.

This theory fits with this work because it serves as a guide for promoting the sanctity of life and fairness, and for ensuring that in-vitro fertilisation is used in ways that align with moral principles that are not in conflict with societal values that guide our conduct. The theory is entirely opposed to the commercialisation of children.

The Process of In-Vitro Fertilisation

The consequence of the inability to give birth among couples is on the increase, and most couples are prone to psychological stress resulting in anxiety, insecurity in marriage, fear, depression, seclusion/isolation, shame/disgrace, disorientation, physical pain, disheartening, and the mental well-being of couples in such conditions is adversely affected. Clients involved in in-vitro fertilisation do so in secrecy to avoid stigmatisation and to preserve their self-esteem.

The two procedures of handling infertility medically can be recapitulated thus: the first is that which is referred to as the conventional method of treatment, and this involves the use of medication and surgery (Gold, 2001). The second way is called unconventional treatment, which experts call artificial reproductive technology, whereby artificial insemination, in vitro fertilisation and other ways exist. This method involves the transportation of sperm directly

to the uterus or cervix intending to be pregnant by the couples in need of a child or children.

Vaughn (2017) outlined the process of in-vitro fertilisation to consist of five main steps, and it is outlined below:

1. **Ovarian Stimulation (Superovulation):** At this stage, the woman proceeds by taking ovulation stimulants – fertility drugs to hasten her ovaries to yield several eggs at once instead of the normal one per month. Customary in-vitro fertilisation procedures require multiple eggs to overcome the challenges of defective eggs that might occur during this stage. Fett (2014) made it clear that any successful pregnancy begins with improving egg quality, addressing fertility challenges, and preventing miscarriage.
2. **Egg Retrieval:** This is when eggs are extracted from the egg sac, or follicles, of the ovaries, usually a 30-minute outpatient surgery. This typically takes place when the eggs are ready. The process involves an ultrasound-guided needle inserted into the vagina, through the vagina wall and into the ovaries to the egg-bearing follicles. The eggs are suctioned one by one out through the needle (Vaughn (2017)).
3. **Insemination/Fertilisation:** At this stage, the retrieved eggs are scrutinized, and the ones adjudicated to be of highest worth are mixed with sperm (a step called insemination), which results within a few hours in sperm cells penetrating the eggs (fertilisation). Some eggs will not fertilise, and sometimes none will. Sometimes, the opportunity for fertilisation is significantly increased by a technique identified as Intracytoplasmic Sperm Injection (ICSI), in which an egg is pierced, and a single sperm cell is injected into it.
4. **Embryo Culture:** The embryos grow in a culture medium after fertilisation. Within 48 hours, each consists of 2 to 4 cells; 6 to 10 cells in three days. On the third day, fertilisation experts can examine the embryos for genetic disease using a Pre-implantation Genetic Diagnosis (PGD) technique. Then, only embryos discovered to be free of substandard genes are selected to be transferred to the uterus.
5. **Embryo Transfer:** Embryos are moved into the uterus in the doctor's office up to six days after egg retrieval. Delivery of embryos to the uterus is usually painless. Two or more embryos are normally transferred at once into the uterus to increase the chances of pregnancy. The embryos and the fluids surrounding them are placed in a long straw-like tube called a transfer catheter. Then the catheter is eased into the vagina and through the cervix, and the embryos are pushed from the tube into the uterus.

Ethical Issues in In-Vitro Fertilisation

Ethics examines the methodical reflection on human principles and actions. In the real sense of it, ethics deals with facts and values. In-vitro fertilisation, as good as the intention of the technology may be, has raised many ethical concerns. The concerns started when the first child born through in-vitro fertilization was announced in 1978 (Peterson et al., 2014).

1. Frozen/Destruction of Embryo

After fertilization, unused embryos that are still viable are frequently frozen so that they can be preserved for future use, and those that are defective are destroyed. Destruction of embryos is morally wrong because it is life itself that is being destroyed. The ethical questions that arose with frozen embryos are: for how long do the clinics store them and at what conditions, knowing fully well the problem of power supply in Nigeria? Research from developed countries has revealed that the sustainability of frozen embryos is reduced with longer storage time. Do they get donated to someone else, or will they be destroyed? If destroyed, this raises a serious ethical concern (Omokanye et al., 2017).

The use of third-party gamete is contentious in African society. Bello et al. (2014), in a study in Ibadan, Nigeria, discovered that only 35.2% of men and 24% of women are open to accepting donated eggs and sperm, respectively. The ethical issues surrounding handling surplus embryos have been under serious debate. However, four possible ways were suggested (Paul et al., 2010): thawing and discarding, donating to research, indefinite storage, and donating the embryos to another couple for uterine transfer.

2. Egg and Sperm Donation

Accidental incest may happen in a situation with the possibility of having multiple children fathered by a single sperm donor. Osakwe (2017) told the story of a 21-year-old University of Lagos undergraduate who was a regular sperm donor at a popular clinic for one year. He came across an article in the newspaper of a man in the United Kingdom rumoured to have fathered 800 children, and this caused him to fear that he too may have fathered 500 children, and this got him worried about the possibility of his children getting married to each other in the future and invariably, he may one day, accidentally had sex with his daughter. According to Barnes et al. (2024), the primary ethical concern raised on gamete donation is the potential risk of incest in the future. The one donating the gamete should be aware of what they are doing with the gamete and to what extent.

3. The Challenge of Laboratory Procreation

This is an ethical issue that makes people desist from the use of this technology because embryos are created in the laboratory. This presupposes that embryos are produced like a commodity for customers. Hence, human beings are reduced to mere commodities for patronage. Fertilization takes place outside the traditional process of sexual intercourse created by God.

4. Commercialisation/Commodification of Human Beings

The challenge of commercialization of human beings is another ethical issue. In-vitro fertilisation is virtually placed in the market system of demand and supply. This makes for reimbursement of gemmate donors and the selling of embryos. Ethical questions include equity, possible exploitation of need and other components of marketing ethics. When a woman decides to donate her eggs or a man's sperm, some people can infer that this is the buying and selling of human beings or the makeup of humans (Ola, 2012). In the process, money exchanged hands, which implies buying and selling – reimbursement/compensation.

5. Human Dignity

The ethical issues of equal value, equal human rights and non-discrimination are crucial. Human dignity should be preserved and respected. Human life should not be treated without respect and sanctity. In the words of Olojede (2022), the human embryo is a living member of the homo-sapiens in the earliest stages of development. Thus, as a matter of fundamental justice, a possessor of innate dignity and a right to life. Therefore, the process of in-vitro fertilisation must take into cognisance human embryo is life itself and deserves to be treatment with a sense of human right.

6. Client's Privacy and Data Protection

This is an ethical aspect of the in-vitro fertilisation process that should adhered to. Barnes et al. (2024) clarified that all the respondents in their study stressed the need to protect clients' privacy and data. Every client deserves to be protected. Their records must be kept secret and confidential. This problem of client's privacy and data protection has made many infertile couples to stay away from the process of in-vitro fertilisation.

7. Informed Consent

A client's consent is germane to give permission and acceptance to undergo the in-vitro fertilisation service. However, this is not always so, as there are no

specific developed ethical guidelines to provide specific content for obtaining informed consent in the specialized area of in-vitro service provision (Barnes et al., 2024). Most clients that engage in the process of in-vitro fertilisation may not have access to certain information as to the negative effects of the process. Most times, fertility centers are after the money they can make through the process. The question is that how truly informed are the clients in order to make adequate decision in respect to the process? The giving of consent form does not mean one has all the information necessary for in-vitro fertilisation process. Some have development several sicknesses as a result of going through the process.

8. Single Women and Same-sex Couples

This is another aspect of in-vitro fertilisation that raises an ethical dilemma. According to Asplund (2020), moral arguments for and against in-vitro fertilisation in singles and homosexuals are based on fairness, non-discrimination, reproductive autonomy, and children's well-being. It should be noted that legal restrictions on in-vitro fertilisation concerning singles and same-sex couples vary from country to country. However, most Nigerians are never in support of single women and same-sex couples using in-vitro fertilisation process as a means of bearing children. Ethically, it is not morally right and it is an abuse of God's way of procreation.

9. Succession

The practice of in-vitro fertilisation raises the question as to whether children who were fertilised by another man's sperm are entitled to inherit from the estate of their social father (pater) rather than their biological father (genitor), especially in cases where the putative father died intestate (Obagboye & James, 2022). In African setting descent continuity must be maintain and planned for. It is one aspect of Africa culture to maintain one's lineage (generation). Hence, Africans belief that children born through the process of in-vitro fertilisation are not truly one's biological children. This calls for adequate education and enlightenment for people in African setting to understand and accept in-vitro fertilisation as a way of solving the problem of infertility.

10. Surrogacy and Gestational Carriers

The use of in-vitro fertilisation for commercial surrogacy and gestational carriers raises another ethical issue. Surrogacy has to do with a woman who agrees to carry a pregnancy using her oocytes but the sperm of another couple and is willing to surrender the child to the couple upon delivery (James, 2010).

James further explained that a gestational carrier is a woman who agrees to carry a resultant embryo of a couple who undergo in-vitro fertilization with their egg and sperm, and such gestational carrier carries the pregnancy and relinquishes the child to the couple upon delivery. These two approaches are also seen as a form of “child selling; or the “sale of parental rights.”

Socio-Ethical Implications of In-Vitro Fertilisation

Nigeria society believed that childbearing is germane to stabilizing the family and preserving family lineage. However, there are some socio-ethical implications associated with going through the process of in-vitro fertilisation to bear children. It has to do with some socio-ethical relationship defined by moral values of the society towards one another.

1. **Violation of the Natural Method of Procreation:** The process of in-vitro fertilisation brings to bear the unnatural procedure involved. This raises some concern among people because the process violates the natural method of conception as it engages external individuals in human creation. However, some others see the process as a means of helping those who are infertile to have their children.
2. **Embryos Disposal:** One major issue with the use of in-vitro fertilisation concerning morality is the personhood of unused embryos. There is the process of abortion and fetus manipulation. More eggs are extracted and fertilized than matured and transferred (Beers, 2019). It is God who determines who lives or dies.
3. **Child Commodification:** Beers (2019) clarified that many have opposed in-vitro fertilisation because it makes a child substitutable - a mere manufactured commodity. Beers further explained that the child seeks to fulfil the intended parent’s desires rather than to be an end-in-him/herself. Child bearing is now seen as one going to supermarket to buy a product of your choice. Money is now the determinant, as it serves as the purchasing power to having a child.
4. **The Use of Other Person’s Egg or Sperm:** Some believed that since the method aimed at helping infertile couples to have their children, the procedure should be appreciated. However, some thought that the decision should be left in the hands of the couples because they are in the best position to determine its goodness or depravity. As long as the couples agree to use the process, it should be seen as a form of adoption. The reason is that if adoption should be encouraged, how much more is the use of other people’s sperm or egg (Abioye, 2020)? Religions in African settings did not approve the use of an external person’s egg or sperm for infertile

couples. Abioye further explained that whenever other people's eggs or sperm are used for another couple, there is a tendency for an emotional crisis in the future because the situation will always linger in the mind of both the husband and wife.

5. **Emotional Trauma:** According to Hampshire & Simpson (2015), the consequences of infertility and childlessness can be manifold at personal, marital, family, and community levels, as well as financial. Nevertheless, with all these efforts and money invested in accomplishing a pregnancy and a child, having children through in-vitro fertilisation is considered to be inferior and is often highly stigmatised. Even children conceived through the process are likely to face greater emotional trauma (Abioye, 2020). Adversely, some couples may not be affected by such emotional trauma, primarily if they have achieved their aim. However, because of the value placed on reproduction through sexual intercourse in African society, the concerned couple may feel inferior for the inability to conceive using the natural process.
6. **Societal Perception:** There are conflicting opinions and perspectives on the subject of in-vitro fertilisation. Some are of the view that children born through in-vitro fertilisation are not normal. Abioye (2020) observed that Nigeria society, especially in Yoruba culture, might not regard any child born through in-vitro fertilisation as a normal child. Such a child is not seen as the result of the handiwork of conventional method of child bearing. In Perry's (2018) words about the nature of human beings, God created humankind in his image and asked them to rule. It is like God saying to the whole creation that he is still reigning and ruling; therefore, humanity is tasked to carry out this role through God's authority. This means that God's image in man is not the attribute possessed by man according to his will but by God's desire. However, God has given man the ability to be co-creator with him, so in-vitro fertilisation is God's revelation to man to bring joy to those facing the challenges of childlessness.
7. **Abolishment of Social Structures:** In the opinion of Ijeudo & Obeta (2017), in-vitro fertilisation would lead to the end of the nuclear family, with marriage placed by laboratory breeding. There tends to exist fear of the creation of all sorts of non-traditional families. At the same time, some worry that the new technology enabling women to bear children creates the opportunity for a single woman, even a lesbian couple, to bear children. This destroys family structure where a father and mother are responsible for parenting their children.

- 8. *Marginalisation Based on Income:*** According to Hocker (2020), in-vitro fertilisation drives the problem of marginalization based on wealth. In-vitro fertilisation is very costly and may not be successful the first or second time. Genetic testing may be accomplished for an additional cost. Concerning the high cost of in-vitro fertilisation, low-income individuals may not be able to access it, and this shows that those who do not have such an amount will not be able to access the process. Hence, it is not a fair system to decide who has access to undertake in-vitro fertilisation based on income. In such a situation, one's conditions regulate who is qualified to be a parent. It is glaring that only those who can afford in-vitro fertilisation can fulfil their dream of having their children.

Conclusion

This study showed that in-vitro fertilisation gives hope to couples who are faced with the difficulty of bearing their own children but the process is not without some socio-ethical dilemmas. In-vitro fertilisation as a means of child bearing is often contested in Nigeria cultural setting even though high premium is placed in child bearing. This is because it contradicts conventional method of child bearing, lineage, and the sanctity human life. This study identified some socio-ethical issues that need serious attention in order for in-vitro fertilisation to serve as a genuine solution to the challenge of infertility in Nigeria. The process of in-vitro fertilisation must be done in ways that ethical procedure are properly accepted by the society.

Some ethical concerns surrounding in-vitro fertilisation include frozen/destruction of embryo, the use of other person's egg/sperm, the challenge of laboratory procreation, human dignity, problem of succession/descent continuity, surrogacy, embryo disposal, and child commodification. These has made many Nigeria society to view in-vitro fertilisation with misgiving. This work, therefore concludes that sound ethical framework is necessary for adequate integration of in-vitro fertilisation in Nigeria context. This also, call for adequate enlightenment and campaign in the society where religious, social and community leaders should be fully involved. This will serve as a means of reaching out to persons in the society that has influence on the general populace and will enhance Nigeria society involvement while navigating the complexities of in-vitro fertilisation.

Recommendations

This study recommended as follows:

1. **Standard Ethical Guidelines:** Establishment of standard ethical procedure to guide the practice of in-vitro fertilisation will help promote the usefulness of the process in the contemporary society. These guidelines should involve handling of embryos, commodification of the process, the use of third party egg/sperm, issue of surrogacy, and embryo disposal. Such ethical guidelines reduce socio-ethical dilemmas associated with in-vitro fertilisation.
2. **Dialogue:** Interdisciplinary dialogue should be promoted by government where scholars, bioethics, religious leaders, community leaders and medical practitioners can come together to examine the relevance of in-vitro fertilisation and its benefits in handling the problem of infertility.
3. **Enlightenment:** Religious and community leaders should educate their people that in-vitro fertilisation is a solution to the problem of infertility and as such God in His wisdom gave man knowledge on how to meet the need of those going through the challenge of infertility. This will reduce emotional trauma that comes from stigmatisation and rejection from the society.

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